

Low-Calorie Diet Versus Time-Restricted Eating in the Pursuit of Diabetes Remission: A Comparative Review

ABSTRACT

Background /Objectives: Type 2 diabetes mellitus remains a major global health challenge, with prevalence rising faster than treatment and remission rates. Among emerging dietary interventions for diabetes remission, low-calorie diet (LCD) and time-restricted eating (TRE) have gained attention, though they differ in physiological mechanisms and real-world feasibility. This review compares LCD and TRE in terms of physiological mechanisms, clinical outcomes, and real-world implementation for type 2 diabetes remission, with emphasis on underserved and circadian-disrupted populations.

Methods: A narrative synthesis of key clinical trials and emerging studies was conducted, comparing the effects of LCD and TRE on intra-organ fat reduction, insulin sensitivity, circadian alignment, and diabetes remission. Special focus was placed on real-world applicability and populations affected by circadian disruption.

Results: LCD has demonstrated high remission rates in trials such as DiRECT, though sustaining long-term adherence remains challenging. TRE, a circadian-aligned approach, may improve glycemic control and metabolic outcomes without strict calorie counting; however, large-scale, long-term remission evidence remains limited.

Conclusion: LCD and TRE are promising but distinct dietary strategies for diabetes remission. While LCD has robust clinical support, TRE offers a scalable, lifestyle-friendly alternative. Comparative, real-world studies are needed to guide personalized and equitable diabetes care.

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes remission; low-calorie diet; time-restricted eating; lifestyle intervention; metabolic health; shift work; circadian rhythm; adherence; public health.

INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes mellitus, a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by insulin resistance and hyperglycemia [1], persistently remains a major global health burden, directly causing 3.4 million deaths annually [2], with prevalence projected to exceed 1.31 billion cases worldwide by 2050 [3]. Dietary intervention is a cornerstone of type 2 diabetes management and is considered highly cost-effective [4,5].

Diet as a primary intervention can achieve type 2 diabetes remission, which is a reversal of high blood glucose levels to below diagnostic threshold without the need of medication [4–6]. Low-calorie diet (LCD), particularly, has been demonstrated to significantly induce weight loss, improve glycemic control and achieve diabetes remission, which has been a basis for the implementation of the NHS Type 2 Diabetes Path to Remission Programme (formerly Low Calorie Diet Programme), as a pilot treatment for the self-management of type 2 diabetes in overweight and obese type 2 diabetes patients, based on the success of the DiRECT and DROPLET clinical trials [7,8]. However, over the decades, diabetes intervention trials have also shown that sustaining daily caloric restriction long-term can be challenging [9].

Like LCD, time-restricted eating (TRE), a form of chrono nutrition which involves confining the eating window to 4 -10 hours per day and fasting for the prolonged remaining hours of the day, has recently gained attention, for the management of obesity and type 2 diabetes, due to the lack of need for calorie counting or restriction, and easy compliance with eating schedules [10]. Emerging evidence suggests TRE can support weight loss and improve fasting and postprandial

glucose levels, with some early studies indicating potential for diabetes remission. [10–13]. Importantly, TRE is distinct from intermittent fasting (IF), which involves alternating fasting and feeding periods across days (e.g., 5:2 diet, alternate-day fasting). Although often conflated with IF, TRE represents a distinct dietary strategy. The key differences between TRE and IF are summarized in Table 1.

Feature	Time Restricted Eating (TRE)	Intermittent Fasting (IF)
Definition	Daily eating pattern confined to a daily window of 4 - 10 hours and fasting during the remaining hours [14].	Broad term for eating patterns characterized by alternating periods of eating and fasting across days [15]
Calorie Restriction	Not mandatory. Focus is on timing, although spontaneous calorie reduction may occur [16].	Often involves reduced calorie intake on fasting days.
Circadian Alignment	Strongly linked with circadian rhythm, meal timing aligns with biological clock.	Less directly tied to circadian cycles. Fasting may occur independent of biological rhythms.
Mechanisms	Synchronizes metabolic processes with the light-dark cycle, thereby improving insulin sensitivity, supporting metabolic switching, reducing inflammation, and restoring glucose tolerance [17,18]. Basically, TRE confines food intake with a specific time window, usually during periods of peak insulin sensitivity [19].	Promotes metabolic switching, autophagy, and potential cardiometabolic benefits by alternating between fasting and feeding periods. This enables a shift from glucose to fat as the primary fuel source, supporting metabolic flexibility [17,19,20].

Adherence Profile	Often perceived as simpler (no calorie counting, consistent daily routine).	May be harder to sustain due to alternating fasting/feeding schedules.
--------------------------	---	--

Table 1. Distinction between Time-Restricted Eating and Intermittent Fasting. Data adapted from [14–20].

This distinction is important because TRE’s daily, circadian-aligned eating pattern may offer greater real-world feasibility for type 2 diabetes management compared to the alternating fasting schedules typical of IF. Clarifying this distinction ensures that TRE is evaluated on its own merits, rather than conflated with broader IF regimens.

The Clinical Relevance of Diabetes Remission

Type 2 diabetes rarely occurs in isolation. It is accompanied by several comorbidities and complications, including cardiovascular diseases, chronic kidney disease, nerve damage, impaired vision that can progress into blindness, fatty liver disease, cancer, cognitive impairments, oral health problems, feet problems that can be progressive into amputation, lower quality of life and mental health [21,22]. Due to its complex pathophysiology and genetic-environmental interactions, a partial, complete, or prolonged remission would be beneficial because of the lower blood glucose range, subsequently lowering the risk of diabetes related complications, comorbidities and mortality [23]. Studies have also shown that short-term diabetes remission is linked with long-term health benefits [24,25].

Why Compare Low-Calorie Diet and Time-Restricted Eating?

LCD and TRE have become popular approaches for weight loss and glycemic management. While LCD has been implemented into diabetes care by the NHS, TRE is still being explored with some

studies affirming its potential for diabetes remission and feasibility in the real world due to its ease of compliance with eating schedules [10,26,27].

This review compares the mechanisms, evidence, and real-world applicability of LCD and TRE, in the pursuit of type 2 diabetes remission, with particular emphasis on feasibility in high-risk and underserved populations.

MECHANISMS OF ACTION

The pancreas maintains glucose homeostasis by producing the hormones insulin (in β -cells of the Islets of Langerhans) and glucagon (in α -cells of the Islets of Langerhans), which signal the liver to regulate the blood glucose level [28]. When glucose is elevated, the liver stores the excess glucose through glycogenesis, and during hypoglycemia, it releases glucose through glycogenolysis to maintain normoglycemia [28,29]. One hallmark of type 2 diabetes is the accumulation of excess intra-organ (visceral or ectopic) fat within the liver and pancreas [30,31]. This lipid accumulation impairs hepatic insulin sensitivity and disrupts pancreatic β -cell function [31]. However, clinical evidence particularly from bariatric surgery demonstrates that this dysfunction can be reversed through targeted fat reduction [32].

LCD, typically defined by a daily intake of 800 - 1200kcal, induces rapid weight loss and significantly reduces intra-organ fat [33,34]. This reduction improves liver insulin sensitivity and pancreatic β -cell function [33,35]. Together, these changes contribute to improved glucose regulation and remission of type 2 diabetes [7,8].

TRE, a chrono-nutrition dietary pattern, has been associated with favorable metabolic effects [36]. Proposed mechanisms include improved alignment of circadian rhythms, enhanced insulin sensitivity, reduced systemic inflammation, and promotion of metabolic switching from glucose

to lipid or ketone utilization during fasting periods [37,38]. However, these mechanisms remain incompletely understood and may vary depending on the length and timing of the eating window. Importantly, studies have observed that TRE often produces modest spontaneous caloric restriction, raising questions about whether its metabolic benefits are driven by timing alone or a combination of timing and reduced energy intake [16].

Early randomized controlled trials (RCTs) in patients with type 2 diabetes suggest TRE can improve fasting glucose and insulin sensitivity [26,39], although long-term remission outcomes remain to be established [13,25]. These findings indicate that, while LCDs achieve remission primarily via rapid intra-organ fat loss, TRE may exert benefits through a combination of circadian alignment, improved metabolic flexibility, and unintentional caloric restriction.

Feature	Low-Calorie Diet (LCD)	Time-Restricted Eating (TRE).
Energy Balance	Creates large, intentional calorie deficit (typically 800–1200 kcal/day). [34]	No mandatory calorie restriction, although modest spontaneous reduction often occurs [16].
Weight Loss & Intra-Organ Fat	Rapid weight and intra-organ (liver/pancreas) fat loss, restoring hepatic insulin sensitivity and β -cell function [40].	May reduce body weight and visceral fat gradually, since no active caloric restriction is imposed.
Insulin Sensitivity	Improves hepatic and peripheral insulin sensitivity through fat reduction.	May improve insulin sensitivity via circadian alignment and prolonged fasting intervals.
Metabolic Switching	Driven primarily by negative energy balance [40].	Promote shift from glucose to lipid or ketone metabolism during fasting periods [18].

Circadian Alignment	Not inherently circadian based, eating can occur at any time.	Eating confined to daily window (usually 4-10hours), aligns intake with circadian rhythm.
Adherence	Often challenging, requires calorie tracking, structured meal planning, and ongoing support.	Often simpler, daily routine-based, no calorie counting, but may be harder for irregular schedules (for example, shift workers).

Table 2. Proposed Mechanisms of Type 2 Diabetes Remission in Low-Calorie Diet versus Time-Restricted Eating [16,18,34,40].

CLINICAL EVIDENCE

While LCD interventions have robust randomized trial support, emerging evidence indicates that TRE may also play a promising role in type 2 diabetes management and potential remission. Caloric restriction has consistently been shown to improve glycemic control, promote substantial weight loss, and delay diabetes-related complications [7,8,41]. In particular, the Diabetes Remission Clinical Trial (DiRECT) by Lean et al. (2018) demonstrated the effectiveness and real-world transferability of LCD in primary care settings. Conducted across 49 practices with 306 participants, the trial found that 46% of those in the intervention group achieved diabetes remission and discontinued diabetes medications. At 12 months, participants lost an average of 10 ± 8 kg, and sustained remission was linked to sustained weight loss over 5 years [42,43].

Building on the success of DiRECT and DROPLET trials, the NHS introduced the Type 2 Diabetes Path to Remission Programme, delivered digitally by Oviva, and explored real-world outcomes with more diverse populations, targeting overweight and obese individuals including those in socioeconomically deprived areas of England. Early findings demonstrated significant weight loss,

improved HbA1c, and reduced medication use, confirming the treatment feasibility in real-world practice [44,45].

By contrast, clinical evidence for TRE is more recent but growing steadily. Early pilot and short-term RCTs have suggested that TRE can improve insulin sensitivity, fasting glucose, and glycemic variability in individuals with type 2 diabetes [46–48]. For example, Kahleova et al. (2014) found that consuming two meals per day in a time-restricted pattern improved insulin sensitivity, fasting plasma glucose, hepatic fat content and body weight compared with six meals daily. Likewise, Andriessen et al. (2022) demonstrated that 3 weeks of early TRE (10hours eating window) improved 24-hour glucose levels, fasting glucose, and prolonged the time spent in normoglycemia in adults with type 2 diabetes as compared with spreading daily food intake over at least 14 hours. Parr et al. (2024) RCT provides one of the strongest and most recent controlled evaluations of TRE in this population. In 51 adults with type 2 diabetes randomized to either TRE or standard dietetic care over 6 months, the TRE group showed significantly greater improvements in HbA1c, fasting glucose and reported higher adherence, confirming both efficacy and practicality of this approach in a clinical setting.

In addition to RCTs, several non-randomized and longitudinal studies have provided further real-world insight into TRE's potential for diabetes remission. Idris (2023) reported that among 36 patients who practiced TRE for 3 months, 90% reduced their diabetes medications, 55% of which achieved diabetes remission and maintained it for at least one year, even among participants with diabetes duration greater than 6 years, an encouraging contrast to DiRECT, which primarily included participants with diabetes less than 6 years [8]. Similarly, Rastogi et al. (2024) observed significant improvements in body weight, BMI, fasting glucose, postprandial glucose, and HbA1c after 18 months of TRE in 273 patients with type 2 diabetes, reinforcing TRE's potential as an

effective strategy for diabetes management. A large population-based cohort analysis by Dambha-Miller et al. (2023) also found that partial and complete diabetes remission trajectories were associated with lower long-term complication risk, supporting the broader clinical relevance of remission-based dietary interventions.

Together, these findings suggest that while LCD currently has the most extensive randomized evidence and established implementation pathways, TRE offers a promising, circadian-aligned alternative that may achieve comparable metabolic benefits with potentially greater adherence and acceptability. However, large, long-duration RCTs directly assessing TRE's ability to induce and sustain remission are still needed.

REAL-WORLD APPLICATION

While LCDs remain an effective clinical strategy for inducing type 2 diabetes remission, their long-term sustainability poses significant challenges, particularly without intensive behavioral and dietetic support [9,49]. Although digital platforms have improved accessibility, barriers remain in uptake and adherence due to the demands of calorie tracking, intense and persistent hunger, and various behavioral, psychological, social, and environmental factors [49]. These challenges are especially concerning given that, despite over 630 million people now living with diabetes globally since 1990, treatment coverage has not increased proportionally to the rise in prevalence [50]. Consequently, there is an urgent need for complementary approaches that enhance long-term adherence and real-world scalability of diabetes remission strategies.

TRE offers a potentially more sustainable, lower-cost, and behaviorally simpler alternative. Unlike LCD, TRE does not require calorie counting or meal replacements and preliminary studies suggest that it can be effectively integrated with digital health delivery [27]. However, because TRE

efficacy depends on circadian alignment, its long-term feasibility and adherence, particularly among night-shift workers and metabolically diverse populations, require further evaluation.

Why This Matters in Underserved Populations

Night shift workers represent an underserved and at-risk population for type 2 diabetes, primarily due to circadian disruption and irregular eating schedules [9,51]. Alarming, up to 20% of the global workforce now engages in night-shift work [52]. Beyond personal health risks, poor metabolic control in this group also carries significant economic implications for employers and the healthcare systems [51].

Research indicates that insulin secretion in response to meals is significantly impaired during the biological night [53], and accumulating evidence suggests that TRE may confer the greatest benefits when food intake is aligned with endogenous circadian rhythms [51,54]. Tailoring TRE interventions to accommodate the unique physiological and occupational constraints of shift workers could therefore bridge critical evidence and equity gaps in diabetes care, particularly in socioeconomically deprived or high-risk populations.

These insights highlight the need for inclusive, personalized or context-sensitive dietary strategies that reflect real-world conditions and population diversity, moving beyond controlled trial settings toward equitable, scalable solutions for diabetes care.

ADHERENCE CONSIDERATIONS

While both LCD and TRE have demonstrated promising potential for type 2 diabetes remission, their real-world effectiveness ultimately depends on sustained adherence. LCD often requires continuous calorie tracking, structured meal planning, and frequent professional support, which are factors that can be difficult to maintain outside controlled research settings or intensive primary

care programmes. In contrast, TRE offers greater behavioral simplicity but may present challenges for individuals with irregular daily routines, such as night-shift workers, caregivers, or those experiencing social and occupational disruptions to eating patterns.

To enhance adherence and accessibility, particularly among underserved or high-risk populations, the integration of community health workers (CHWs) or trained health coaches could play a pivotal role. These professionals, often embedded within local communities, can deliver culturally sensitive education, personalized guidance, and consistent follow-up to individuals implementing LCD or TRE interventions. Evidence from lifestyle intervention programs indicates that community-based and peer-supported models improve engagement, self-efficacy, and metabolic outcomes, especially in groups facing socioeconomic, occupational, or digital access barriers [55,56].

Embedding such support structures within existing healthcare systems may reduce attrition, boost motivation, and help individuals overcome practical barriers such as irregular schedules, food insecurity, or limited digital literacy. Ultimately, this person-centered approach could strengthen the real-world scalability and sustainability of dietary remission strategies.

CONCLUSION

Both LCD and TRE represent promising, evidence-based nutritional strategies for achieving remission in type 2 diabetes. LCD interventions have demonstrated robust clinical efficacy, particularly within structured programs and digital delivery models such as the DiRECT and NHS remission pathways. However, sustaining long-term adherence beyond supervised intervention periods remains a major challenge.

In contrast, TRE provides a simpler, circadian-aligned alternative that may enhance feasibility and acceptability in everyday life. Growing clinical and observational evidence supports its potential to improve body weight, glycemic control, and insulin sensitivity, though large-scale randomized controlled trials assessing remission outcomes and long-term sustainability are still limited.

Overall, both dietary strategies hold significant potential in the global effort to reverse type 2 diabetes and mitigate its health and economic burden. Integrating these approaches with digital health tools, behavioral support, and culturally tailored implementation strategies may improve adherence, scalability, and real-world impact. Future comparative and longitudinal trials are essential to determine which strategy, or combination, offers the most durable benefit across diverse populations, including shift workers and underserved communities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, or publication of this article. During the preparation of this manuscript, the author used ChatGPT (OpenAI) for language refinement, reference formatting, and content structuring. All AI-assisted outputs were reviewed and edited for accuracy, and the author takes full responsibility for the content of this publication.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization: Abigael Blessing Kuponyi

Writing - Original Draft: Abigael Blessing Kuponyi

Writing - Review & Editing: Abigael Blessing Kuponyi

Visualization: Abigael Blessing Kuponyi

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

TRE - Time-Restricted Eating

LCD - Low-Calorie Diet

NHS - National Health Service

DiRECT - Diabetes Remission Clinical Trial

DROPLET - Doctor Referral of Overweight People to Low-Energy Treatment

IF - Intermittent Fasting

RCT - Randomized Controlled Trial

HbA1c - Glycated Hemoglobin

CHW - Community Health Worker

REFERENCES

1. Classification and Diagnosis of Diabetes Mellitus and Other Categories of Glucose Intolerance. *Diabetes* **1979**, *28*, 1039–1057, doi:10.2337/diab.28.12.1039.
2. International Diabetes Federation IDF Diabetes Atlas 2025 11th Edn. Brussels, Belgium. .
3. Ong, K.L.; Stafford, L.K.; McLaughlin, S.A.; Boyko, E.J.; Vollset, S.E.; Smith, A.E.; Dalton, B.E.; Duprey, J.; Cruz, J.A.; Hagins, H.; et al. Global, Regional, and National Burden of Diabetes from 1990 to 2021, with Projections of Prevalence to 2050: A Systematic Analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. *The Lancet* **2023**, *402*, 203–234, doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(23)01301-6.

4. Briggs Early, K.; Stanley, K. Position of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics: The Role of Medical Nutrition Therapy and Registered Dietitian Nutritionists in the Prevention and Treatment of Prediabetes and Type 2 Diabetes. *J Acad Nutr Diet* **2018**, *118*, 343–353, doi:10.1016/j.jand.2017.11.021.
5. Rosenfeld, R.M.; Kelly, J.H.; Agarwal, M.; Aspary, K.; Barnett, T.; Davis, B.C.; Fields, D.; Gaillard, T.; Gulati, M.; Guthrie, G.E.; et al. Dietary Interventions to Treat Type 2 Diabetes in Adults with a Goal of Remission: An Expert Consensus Statement from the American College of Lifestyle Medicine. *Am J Lifestyle Med* **2022**, *16*, 342–362, doi:10.1177/15598276221087624.
6. Guilbert, E.; Perry, R.; Whitmarsh, A.; Sauchelli, S. Short-Term Effectiveness of Nutrition Therapy to Treat Type 2 Diabetes in Low-Income and Middle-Income Countries: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomised Controlled Trials. *BMJ Open* **2022**, *12*, e056108, doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2021-056108.
7. Astbury, N.M.; Aveyard, P.; Nickless, A.; Hood, K.; Corfield, K.; Lowe, R.; Jebb, S.A. Doctor Referral of Overweight People to Low Energy Total Diet Replacement Treatment (DROPLET): Pragmatic Randomised Controlled Trial. *BMJ* **2018**, k3760, doi:10.1136/bmj.k3760.
8. Lean, M.E.; Leslie, W.S.; Barnes, A.C.; Brosnahan, N.; Thom, G.; McCombie, L.; Peters, C.; Zhyzhneuskaya, S.; Al-Mrabeh, A.; Hollingsworth, K.G.; et al. Primary Care-Led Weight Management for Remission of Type 2 Diabetes (DiRECT): An Open-Label, Cluster-Randomised Trial. *The Lancet* **2018**, *391*, 541–551, doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(17)33102-1.
9. Vasim, I.; Majeed, C.N.; DeBoer, M.D. Intermittent Fasting and Metabolic Health. *Nutrients* **2022**, *14*, 631, doi:10.3390/nu14030631.
10. Ezpeleta, M.; Cienfuegos, S.; Lin, S.; Pavlou, V.; Gabel, K.; Tussing-Humphreys, L.; Varady, K.A. Time-Restricted Eating: Watching the Clock to Treat Obesity. *Cell Metab* **2024**, *36*, 301–314, doi:10.1016/j.cmet.2023.12.004.
11. Grajower, M.M.; Horne, B.D. Clinical Management of Intermittent Fasting in Patients with Diabetes Mellitus. *Nutrients* **2019**, *11*, 873, doi:10.3390/nu11040873.
12. Varady, K.A. Intermittent versus Daily Calorie Restriction: Which Diet Regimen Is More Effective for Weight Loss? *Obesity Reviews* **2011**, *12*, doi:10.1111/j.1467-789X.2011.00873.x.
13. Idris, I. Time Restricted Eating May Induce Diabetes Remission. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism Now* **2023**, *1*, doi:10.1002/doi2.33.
14. Wilkinson, M.J.; Manoogian, E.N.C.; Zadourian, A.; Lo, H.; Fakhouri, S.; Shoghi, A.; Wang, X.; Fleischer, J.G.; Navlakha, S.; Panda, S.; et al. Ten-Hour Time-Restricted Eating

- Reduces Weight, Blood Pressure, and Atherogenic Lipids in Patients with Metabolic Syndrome. *Cell Metab* **2020**, *31*, 92-104.e5, doi:10.1016/J.CMET.2019.11.004.
15. Sun, M.-L.; Yao, W.; Wang, X.-Y.; Gao, S.; Varady, K.A.; Forslund, S.K.; Zhang, M.; Shi, Z.-Y.; Cao, F.; Zou, B.-J.; et al. Intermittent Fasting and Health Outcomes: An Umbrella Review of Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses of Randomised Controlled Trials. *EClinicalMedicine* **2024**, *70*, 102519, doi:10.1016/j.eclinm.2024.102519.
 16. Gabel, K.; Varady, K.A. Current Research: Effect of Time Restricted Eating on Weight and Cardiometabolic Health. *J Physiol* **2022**, *600*, 1313–1326, doi:10.1113/JP280542.
 17. Vasim, I.; Majeed, C.N.; DeBoer, M.D. Intermittent Fasting and Metabolic Health. *Nutrients* **2022**, *14*, 631, doi:10.3390/nu14030631.
 18. Petersen, M.C.; Gallop, M.R.; Flores Ramos, S.; Zarrinpar, A.; Broussard, J.L.; Chondronikola, M.; Chaix, A.; Klein, S. Complex Physiology and Clinical Implications of Time-Restricted Eating. *Physiol Rev* **2022**, *102*, 1991–2034, doi:10.1152/physrev.00006.2022.
 19. Lekhwani, S.; Das Vaswani, N. The Impact of Chrononutrition on Metabolic Health: Aligning Eating Patterns with Circadian Rhythms. *IP Journal of Nutrition, Metabolism and Health Science* **2024**, *7*, 105–109, doi:10.18231/j.ijnmhs.2024.019.
 20. Shabkhizan, R.; Haiaty, S.; Moslehian, M.S.; Bazmani, A.; Sadeghsoltani, F.; Saghaei Bagheri, H.; Rahbarghazi, R.; Sakhinia, E. The Beneficial and Adverse Effects of Autophagic Response to Caloric Restriction and Fasting. *Advances in Nutrition* **2023**, *14*, 1211–1225, doi:10.1016/j.advnut.2023.07.006.
 21. Chentli, F.; Azzoug, S.; Mahgoun, S. Diabetes Mellitus in Elderly. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab* **2015**, *19*, 744, doi:10.4103/2230-8210.167553.
 22. Clarke, J.; Sanatkar, S.; Baldwin, P.A.; Fletcher, S.; Gunn, J.; Wilhelm, K.; Campbell, L.; Zwar, N.; Harris, M.; Lapsley, H.; et al. A Web-Based Cognitive Behavior Therapy Intervention to Improve Social and Occupational Functioning in Adults With Type 2 Diabetes (The Springboard Trial): Randomized Controlled Trial. *J Med Internet Res* **2019**, *21*, e12246, doi:10.2196/12246.
 23. Vasdeki, D.; Koufakis, T.; Tsamos, G.; Busetto, L.; Zebekakis, P.; Kotsa, K. Remission as an Emerging Therapeutic Target in Type 2 Diabetes in the Era of New Glucose-Lowering Agents: Benefits, Challenges, and Treatment Approaches. *Nutrients* **2022**, *14*, 4801, doi:10.3390/nu14224801.
 24. Yang, X.; Zhou, J.; Shao, H.; Huang, B.; Kang, X.; Wu, R.; Bian, F.; Hu, M.; Liu, D. Effect of an Intermittent Calorie-Restricted Diet on Type 2 Diabetes Remission: A Randomized

- Controlled Trial. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* **2023**, *108*, 1415–1424, doi:10.1210/clinem/dgac661.
25. Dambha-Miller, H.; Hounkpatin, H.O.; Stuart, B.; Farmer, A.; Griffin, S. Type 2 Diabetes Remission Trajectories and Variation in Risk of Diabetes Complications: A Population-Based Cohort Study. *PLoS One* **2023**, *18*, e0290791, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0290791.
 26. Rastogi, S.; Verma, N.; Raghuwanshi, G.S.; Atam, V.; Kumar Verma, D. The Impact of Time-Restricted Meal Intake on Glycemic Control and Weight Management in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients: An 18-Month Longitudinal Study. *Cureus* **2024**, doi:10.7759/cureus.53680.
 27. Manoogian, E.N.C.; Zadourian, A.; Lo, H.C.; Gutierrez, N.R.; Shoghi, A.; Rosander, A.; Pazargadi, A.; Ormiston, C.K.; Wang, X.; Sui, J.; et al. Feasibility of Time-Restricted Eating and Impacts on Cardiometabolic Health in 24-h Shift Workers: The Healthy Heroes Randomized Control Trial. *Cell Metab* **2022**, *34*, 1442-1456.e7, doi:10.1016/j.cmet.2022.08.018.
 28. Wendt, A.; Eliasson, L. Pancreatic Alpha Cells and Glucagon Secretion: Novel Functions and Targets in Glucose Homeostasis. *Curr Opin Pharmacol* **2022**, *63*, 102199, doi:10.1016/J.COPH.2022.102199.
 29. Röder, P. V; Wu, B.; Liu, Y.; Han, W. Pancreatic Regulation of Glucose Homeostasis. *Exp Mol Med* **2016**, *48*, e219–e219, doi:10.1038/emm.2016.6.
 30. Sattar, N.; Gill, J.M. Type 2 Diabetes as a Disease of Ectopic Fat? *BMC Med* **2014**, *12*, 123, doi:10.1186/s12916-014-0123-4.
 31. Chandrasekaran, P.; Weiskirchen, R. The Role of Obesity in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus—An Overview. *Int J Mol Sci* **2024**, *25*, 1882, doi:10.3390/ijms25031882.
 32. Russel, S.M.; Valle, V.; Spagni, G.; Hamilton, S.; Patel, T.; Abdukadyrov, N.; Dong, Y.; Gangemi, A. Physiologic Mechanisms of Type II Diabetes Mellitus Remission Following Bariatric Surgery: A Meta-Analysis and Clinical Implications. *Journal of Gastrointestinal Surgery* **2020**, *24*, 728–741, doi:10.1007/s11605-019-04508-2.
 33. Romeijn, M.M.; Kolen, A.M.; Holthuijsen, D.D.B.; Janssen, L.; Schep, G.; Leclercq, W.K.G.; van Dielen, F.M.H. Effectiveness of a Low-Calorie Diet for Liver Volume Reduction Prior to Bariatric Surgery: A Systematic Review. *Obes Surg* **2021**, *31*, 350–356, doi:10.1007/s11695-020-05070-6.
 34. Low Calorie Diet - an Overview | ScienceDirect Topics Available online: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/medicine-and-dentistry/low-calorie-diet> (accessed on 13 October 2025).

35. Petersen, K.F.; Dufour, S.; Befroy, D.; Lehrke, M.; Hendler, R.E.; Shulman, G.I. Reversal of Nonalcoholic Hepatic Steatosis, Hepatic Insulin Resistance, and Hyperglycemia by Moderate Weight Reduction in Patients With Type 2 Diabetes. *Diabetes* **2005**, *54*, 603–608, doi:10.2337/diabetes.54.3.603.
36. Katsi, V.; Papakonstantinou, I.P.; Soulaïdopoulos, S.; Katsiki, N.; Tsioufis, K. Chrononutrition in Cardiometabolic Health. *J Clin Med* **2022**, *11*, 296, doi:10.3390/jcm11020296.
37. BaHamman, A.S.; Pirzada, A. Timing Matters: The Interplay between Early Mealtime, Circadian Rhythms, Gene Expression, Circadian Hormones, and Metabolism—A Narrative Review. *Clocks Sleep* **2023**, *5*, 507–535, doi:10.3390/clockssleep5030034.
38. Parr, E.B.; Devlin, B.L.; Hawley, J.A. Perspective: Time-Restricted Eating—Integrating the What with the When. *Advances in Nutrition* **2022**, *13*, 699–711, doi:10.1093/ADVANCES/NMAC015.
39. Che, T.; Yan, C.; Tian, D.; Zhang, X.; Liu, X.; Wu, Z. Time-Restricted Feeding Improves Blood Glucose and Insulin Sensitivity in Overweight Patients with Type 2 Diabetes: A Randomised Controlled Trial. *Nutr Metab (Lond)* **2021**, *18*, 88, doi:10.1186/s12986-021-00613-9.
40. Taylor, R. Type 2 Diabetes and Remission: Practical Management Guided by Pathophysiology. *J Intern Med* **2021**, *289*, 754–770, doi:10.1111/joim.13214.
41. Lim, E.L.; Hollingsworth, K.G.; Aribisala, B.S.; Chen, M.J.; Mathers, J.C.; Taylor, R. Reversal of Type 2 Diabetes: Normalisation of Beta Cell Function in Association with Decreased Pancreas and Liver Triacylglycerol. *Diabetologia* **2011**, *54*, 2506–2514, doi:10.1007/s00125-011-2204-7.
42. Lean, M.E.J.; Leslie, W.S.; Barnes, A.C.; Brosnahan, N.; Thom, G.; McCombie, L.; Peters, C.; Zhyzhneuskaya, S.; Al-Mrabeh, A.; Hollingsworth, K.G.; et al. Durability of a Primary Care-Led Weight-Management Intervention for Remission of Type 2 Diabetes: 2-Year Results of the DiRECT Open-Label, Cluster-Randomised Trial. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol* **2019**, *7*, 344–355, doi:10.1016/S2213-8587(19)30068-3.
43. Lean, M.E.; Leslie, W.S.; Barnes, A.C.; Brosnahan, N.; Thom, G.; McCombie, L.; Kelly, T.; Irvine, K.; Peters, C.; Zhyzhneuskaya, S.; et al. 5-Year Follow-up of the Randomised Diabetes Remission Clinical Trial (DiRECT) of Continued Support for Weight Loss Maintenance in the UK: An Extension Study. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol* **2024**, *12*, 233–246, doi:10.1016/S2213-8587(23)00385-6.
44. Miller KH, J.C.N.J.C.S.F. P136 Uptake, Retention & Outcomes in a Digital Low-Calorie Diet Programme Delivered to a Geographically Remote Population Living with Type 2 Diabetes (12 Month Service Evaluation). **2022**.

45. Valabhji, J.; Gorton, T.; Barron, E.; Safazadeh, S.; Earnshaw, F.; Helm, C.; Virr, M.; Kernan, J.; Crowe, S.; Aveyard, P.; et al. Early Findings from the NHS Type 2 Diabetes Path to Remission Programme: A Prospective Evaluation of Real-World Implementation. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol* **2024**, *12*, 653–663, doi:10.1016/S2213-8587(24)00194-3.
46. Kahleova, H.; Belinova, L.; Malinska, H.; Oliyarnyk, O.; Trnovska, J.; Skop, V.; Kazdova, L.; Dezortova, M.; Hajek, M.; Tura, A.; et al. Eating Two Larger Meals a Day (Breakfast and Lunch) Is More Effective than Six Smaller Meals in a Reduced-Energy Regimen for Patients with Type 2 Diabetes: A Randomised Crossover Study. *Diabetologia* **2014**, *57*, 1552–1560, doi:10.1007/s00125-014-3253-5.
47. Andriessen, C.; Fealy, C.E.; Veelen, A.; van Beek, S.M.M.; Roumans, K.H.M.; Connell, N.J.; Mevenkamp, J.; Moonen-Kornips, E.; Havekes, B.; Schrauwen-Hinderling, V.B.; et al. Three Weeks of Time-Restricted Eating Improves Glucose Homeostasis in Adults with Type 2 Diabetes but Does Not Improve Insulin Sensitivity: A Randomised Crossover Trial. *Diabetologia* **2022**, *65*, 1710–1720, doi:10.1007/s00125-022-05752-z.
48. Parr, E.B.; Radford, B.E.; Hall, R.C.; Steventon-Lorenzen, N.; Flint, S.A.; Siviour, Z.; Plessas, C.; Halson, S.L.; Brennan, L.; Kouw, I.W.K.; et al. Comparing the Effects of Time-Restricted Eating on Glycaemic Control in People with Type 2 Diabetes with Standard Dietetic Practice: A Randomised Controlled Trial. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* **2024**, *217*, 111893, doi:10.1016/j.diabres.2024.111893.
49. O'Connor, S.G.; Boyd, P.; Bailey, C.P.; Shams-White, M.M.; Agurs-Collins, T.; Hall, K.; Reedy, J.; Sauter, E.R.; Czajkowski, S.M. Perspective: Time-Restricted Eating Compared with Caloric Restriction: Potential Facilitators and Barriers of Long-Term Weight Loss Maintenance. *Advances in Nutrition* **2021**, *12*, 325–333, doi:10.1093/advances/nmaa168.
50. Zhou, B.; Rayner, A.W.; Gregg, E.W.; Sheffer, K.E.; Carrillo-Larco, R.M.; Bennett, J.E.; Shaw, J.E.; Paciorek, C.J.; Singleton, R.K.; Barradas Pires, A.; et al. Worldwide Trends in Diabetes Prevalence and Treatment from 1990 to 2022: A Pooled Analysis of 1108 Population-Representative Studies with 141 Million Participants. *The Lancet* **2024**, *404*, 2077–2093, doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(24)02317-1.
51. Charlot, A.; Hutt, F.; Sabatier, E.; Zoll, J. Beneficial Effects of Early Time-Restricted Feeding on Metabolic Diseases: Importance of Aligning Food Habits with the Circadian Clock. *Nutrients* **2021**, *13*, 1405, doi:10.3390/nu13051405.
52. International Labour Organization Working Time and Work Organization. ILO Sectoral Brief. **2020**.
53. Garaulet, M.; Lopez-Minguez, J.; Dashti, H.S.; Vetter, C.; Hernández-Martínez, A.M.; Pérez-Ayala, M.; Baraza, J.C.; Wang, W.; Florez, J.C.; Scheer, F.A.J.L.; et al. Interplay of Dinner Timing and *MTNR1B* Type 2 Diabetes Risk Variant on Glucose Tolerance and

- Insulin Secretion: A Randomized Crossover Trial. *Diabetes Care* **2022**, *45*, 512–519, doi:10.2337/dc21-1314.
54. Zeb, F.; Wu, X.; Fatima, S.; Zaman, M.H.; Khan, S.A.; Safdar, M.; Alam, I.; Feng, Q. Time-Restricted Feeding Regulates Molecular Mechanisms with Involvement of Circadian Rhythm to Prevent Metabolic Diseases. *Nutrition* **2021**, *89*, 111244, doi:10.1016/j.nut.2021.111244.
 55. Wayne, N.; Perez, D.F.; Kaplan, D.M.; Ritvo, P. Health Coaching Reduces HbA1c in Type 2 Diabetic Patients From a Lower-Socioeconomic Status Community: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *J Med Internet Res* **2015**, *17*, e224, doi:10.2196/jmir.4871.
 56. Katula, J.A.; Vitolins, M.Z.; Rosenberger, E.L.; Blackwell, C.S.; Morgan, T.M.; Lawlor, M.S.; Goff, D.C. One-Year Results of a Community-Based Translation of the Diabetes Prevention Program. *Diabetes Care* **2011**, *34*, 1451–1457, doi:10.2337/dc10-2115.